

**A MODERN APPROACH TO DEVELOPING A SPIRITUALLY
AND MORALLY SUSTAINABLE ENVIRONMENT IN THE
NEIGHBORHOOD AND FAMILY**

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The purpose of this article: to prevent the negative impact of the negative media on the upbringing of children today, to develop the foundations and abilities of spiritual and moral education, to study and shape the inseparable link between the neighborhood and the family, to educate the younger generation on the basis of our mentality and religion in the spirit of patriotism

Keywords: education, upbringing, society, culture, environment, approach

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The more we are talking about the negative impact of the media on the upbringing of a child at the present time, the more social studies show that the family's spiritual moral environment is considered to be much higher than other factors. Although, of course, here it is necessary to take into account two important conditions: the first is that the possibilities of the family are objectively limited; the second is that the Modern Family, for a number of

reasons, often fails to realize the pedagogical potential of its positive impact on the child.

Today, we demand an in-depth scientific approach to the issue of strengthening neighborhood and family institutions, the use of innovative methods in problem solving, practical cooperation with scientific research institutions and public organizations in the field. Only then we will be able to implement the idea of solving the problems of troubled and disputable families, preparing young people for family life, the criteria of a modern exemplary family, the concept of a “healthy family — a healthy society”. There are also a number of problems that have accumulated over the years in these areas, it is natural that they are all concerned.

Through the study of moral views that have been formed over the centuries and their socio-spiritual roots, various directions of the science of morals in the world and the region and the solution of problems related to spirituality in them, the comparative analysis of the achievements and shortcomings of the world science of morals and the search for ways to solve.

The fact that Uzbekistan considers its prospects and future in the development and care of the family in the era of today's rapidly changing globalization is also evident when the restoration of a modern, exemplary and prosperous family becomes one of the priorities of the state policy, further enriching the above traditional values.

In this place, it is necessary to say openly, no matter how bitter it may be, then factors such as some ill — deeds that are not characteristic of our people-family divorces, various conflicting situations, unemployment, unhealthy environment in the family, moral depression, neediness, cases of touching the crime, create troubled, disadvantaged, etc families and a number of socio-spiritual problems. Especially serious concerns arise in a person when the

number of divorces does not decrease. The following factors are the main causes of the collapse of families in our country:

Psychological factor is a severe psychological environment in the family, lack of mutual understanding, constant conflicts in the family, interference of parents in the life of a young couple, alienation of young spouses, indifference to each other;

Social factor—drinking, childlessness, the fact that the health of a husband or wife is not good;

Moral-moral factor — extramarital relations of one of the spouses for a long time in the continuation;

The economic factor is the lack of satisfactory living conditions, material shortage, unemployment, the inability of the husband to provide the family, the severance of contact with the family of one of the spouses who went abroad as a labor migrant, the inability to extend debts.

All ideas, experiences, new customs, traditions, spiritual and moral values, which are integrated into children in the family, pass through family traditions and serve to form them harmoniously. Continue all the experiences of the ancestors of the new generation past in life to a certain extent through family traditions. The process of upbringing is multifaceted, in fact, the older generation also consists in giving knowledge, experience, skills and habits to the younger generation and passing them along. In the education of children in the family, it is of practical importance to use the national traditions accumulated in the life of the family in accordance with the purpose.

On the other hand, society has gone a long way in developing technological progress. The mass media has a great role to play in the formation of the skills of the information technologies of adults and children; early teaching of computer technology in schools is common. Sociologists who study the sphere of interest and employment of modern children also note that in the

system of the priority of the modern generation, television and computer games are in the first place. However, unfortunately, these technical innovations of modern society do not contribute to the development of communication between children and adults, that is, they do not have a positive effect on the formation of the necessary personal qualities of the younger generation.

In the 21st century, young parents themselves tend to gadgets and internet networks, the lack of communication with close people is a great tragedy, and such a deficit destroys the moral norms of the family and the spirit of humanism.

Gadgets that absorb the life of children are aggressive towards them, depriving them of the ability to perceive the image, providing brighter and clearer images of life. This is due to the fact that in a Modern Family, television (computer, laptop, tablet) has become a habit to hold even in the cradle of the baby, and mothers with babies on their hands are using websites and social networks.

When educating a child, it is important to take into account his age and level. When a child achieves some kind of achievement, one should not rush to see the result. For example, up to two years old they are brought up only with sweet words, through manipulation. Under the age of five, the child learns the environment, the main fact occupies the same age range. During this period, it will be necessary for us to try to become an example from a more practical point of view, to create a healthy family environment.

The next period will require a bit of rigidity and discipline. This period is in adolescence, when the child divides the white and black in the same period. The award for kindness studies the inevitability of punishment for evil at this stage. During this period, when the child is properly guided, accompanied by righteous friends, he is well-mannered, and an important step is taken to be a good people.

After all, parenting and neighborhood education will always be the first and decisive for the child in his life.

Bibliography

1. Karimov I.A. High spirituality is an invincible force. - Tashkent: Spirituality, 2008. - 176 b.

2. I.A.Karimov. "In the 21st century of Uzbekistan: analysis of security, conditions of stability and guarantees of progress". Т., "Uzbekistan", 1997 y, 137-b.

3. Abdulla Avlani. Turkic Gulistan or morality. –Tashkent, publishing house "teacher", 1992 y, 160-b.

4. Eptorauf Fitret. Family or family management procedures. - Tashkent, people's heritage publishing house named after Abdulla Qadiri, 1993 y, up to 149-192 page.

5. I. Sh. Algarov, R.Mamatkulova, H.D.Norkulov "pedagogy of personality vaaila education" T; "publishing house of Science and technology", 2009 year

6. Sabalev or.A. "To provide pedagogical knowledge to parents". - Tashkent, 1977.

7. www.ziyonet.uz

8. <http://islamcenter.uz/articles/view?id=214>